

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.5231 Max: 62.7851	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1223 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 999-800	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:	
DEFINITION Silty soil beneath 1206 and 1205				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1206	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		clay 10% silt 90% sand ____%
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery	<input type="checkbox"/> Nails	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive		
<input type="checkbox"/> Tiles	<input type="checkbox"/> Marble	<input type="checkbox"/> Travertine	<input type="checkbox"/> Ash			
<input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae	<input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones			
<input type="checkbox"/> Dolia	<input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick	<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt	<input type="checkbox"/> Human bones			
<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs	<input type="checkbox"/> Clay	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth			
<input type="checkbox"/> Mortar	<input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum	<input type="checkbox"/> Sand	<input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth			
<input type="checkbox"/> Coins	<input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster	<input type="checkbox"/> Silt	<input type="checkbox"/> Shells			
<input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe	<input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)			
<input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)				
<input type="checkbox"/> Glass						
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original		<input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		unexcavated
Southern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original		<input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		
Western Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		<input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		
Eastern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original		<input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:			Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1206, 1205			Covers: 1001 bedrock (expected)			
Is cut by:			Cuts:			
Is filled by:			Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS UNEXCAVATED						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: Near center at southern edge of excavation, in Room 1 Shape: Irregular						
For layers complete this section: Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): — Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) — Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): — Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North): 			

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

SU 1223 is a silty deposit within room 1 of a structure, which was left unexcavated. It appears to continue under the eastern wall (SU 1185) of the room, + also to underlie the remains of an earlier, semi-circular rubble wall (SU 1206). Though it was not excavated, it appears to sit on the bedrock.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by

S. PARR

on

26.7.10

Revised by

CPM

on

26.7.10

PDFd by

JJM

on

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Entered by

on